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Effects of wood microfiber chemical treatment on mechanical properties of wood/polypropylene composites moulded by injection process

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Abstract: The technological option for developing composite materials appears as a sustainable alternative for the manufacturing industries, allowing the design of new materials with improved physical-mechanical properties. Composites materials formed by treated microfibers on recycled and pigmented polypropylene matrix were produced in a single screw extruder and moulded by injection as test specimens for tensile, flexion, and impact tests, subsequently, the mechanical, thermal and morphological characterization of the composites was carried out. The chemical treatments tested in this work have the purpose of removing oils, waxes, and lignins which cover the natural fibre cell wall external surface. In this way, the treatment will promote an increase in the maximum stress and the modulus of elasticity in tension and bending. Thus, the results obtained show that the composites with eucalyptus microfibers treated with NaClO achieved greater strength and stiffness under tensile, flexural, and impact loads. Finally, it can be affirmed that the treatments have increased the interfacial adhesion of the materials, contributing to the higher shear strength between the phases.

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1. Introduction

The attempt to adapt the concepts of circular economy to the logic of traditional industrial economy necessarily implies the efficient use of resources. Among others, this involves the use of fewer resources in the production of products and services, namely in the reuse of waste and material recycling.

The recycling of non-renewable polymeric materials has been the best solution at the end of the useful life of these materials, considering factors such as the preservation of virgin raw materials, the quality of recycled products, the low cost of production, and the generation of employment and income [1]. The development of

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sustainable composites materials, from recycled polymeric materials and waste from the wood industry, has been allowing reducing the volume of these products is minimising impacts on health and the environment. Polypropylene (PP) is the most recycled polymer in industry, while the furniture industry has increasingly used timber felled from sustainable forest plantations as a eucalypt.

According to Zaaba and Ismail [2], a great interest in the use of natural wastes as reinforcement of composites has been verified recently for the reduction in the waste of noble materials, since the disposal involves costs of planning, execution, and monitoring in the process of transport and storage of these materials. In Brazil, a large part of these residual volumes come from eucalyptus wood [3] which represents 17-38% when compared to wood biomass [4]. The fast growth and high productivity of eucalyptus plantations motivate the use of this raw material in the form of fibres or microfibres as composite reinforcement in industrial applications. However, a significant disadvantage of natural fibres is their reduced adhesion to the polymeric matrix. Despite their limitations, the application of these materials has increased in several sectors, such as the construction and automotive industry [5]. Several chemical methods have been used to increase fibre-matrix adhesion, which include silanization, dewaxing, acetylation, latex coating, steam explosion, alkalinisation, bleaching, and Gamma radiation [6]. Reichert *et al.* [7] studies showed that pineapple crown microfibres treated with 10% m/v NaOH for 1 hour at 80°C, mixed with recycled polypropylene (rPP) obtained higher tensile modulus of elasticity values than pure rPP, between 672.3 ± 136.0 MPa to 730.7 ± 94.9 MPa, with rPP having 535.2 ± 18.7 MPa. Bogataj *et al.* [8], using bleached cellulose fibres in rPP matrix, obtained tensile strength of 36.0 MPa in comparison with 23.0 MPa for pure rPP, and the tensile modulus of elasticity improved by 16%.

This paper investigated the influence of two treatment methods, alkalinization, and bleaching on the mechanical and thermal properties of composite materials composed of eucalyptus microfibres in a recycled and pigmented polypropylene matrix. Morphological analyses of the microfibres after treatment were carried out, and the results were evaluated by the analysis of variance (ANOVA).

2. Methodology

Recycled polypropylene pigmented with 0.3% m/m carbon black was used as a matrix, with a flow index of 13.097 ± 0.028 g/10 min and density of 0.971 ± 0.001 g cm⁻³. Microfibres (≤ 53 μ m) obtained from the cutting and sanding processing of eucalyptus wood (here identified by F), were subjected to two surface treatments. The first in sodium hydroxide solution (NaOH 10% m/v) for 3 hours at 80°C; now called Fa, and the second in sodium hypochlorite solution (NaClO 12% m/v) at 25°C for 2 hours; identified as Fb. F with density of 0.183 ± 0.012 g cm⁻³, Fa with 0.167 ± 0.019 g cm⁻³ and Fb with 0.158 ± 0.017 g cm⁻³. The incorporation effect of the treated and untreated reforested wood microfibres (10% and 20% m/m), into the rPP matrix, was evaluated. The composites were processed on a SEIBT ES35 L/D 30 single screw extruder, using a screw speed of 90 rpm. The injection moulding machine was a Pavan Zanetti model HXF 220, L/D 22.2, the feed temperature profile for the injection nozzle of 170 (z5), 180 (z4), 190 (z3), 200 (z2), and 210 (z1) °C.

The adhesion between the fibre-matrix interfaces was observed by the fracture surface of the tensile test specimens. A ZEISS® EVO MA10 scanning electron microscope was used to obtain the surface images. The melting

and crystallisation behaviour of the matrix present in the composite was analysed using a NETZSCH STA 449 F3 Jupiter[®] DSC equipment. These samples in alumina crucibles were heated at a rate of 10°C min⁻¹ with a temperature range of 25 to 900°C. The theoretical value of ΔH_m^0 hypothetical of 100% crystalline polypropylene of 209 J g⁻¹ [9] was applied.

3. Results and Discussions

In all conditions, the matrix-reinforcement interaction reduced the tensile strength, compared to the rPP matrix. This can be attributed to the agglomeration of the microfibers acting as stress concentrators, causing rupture of the lower strain material. Moreover, the weak matrix-reinforcement interaction caused by the lack of wettability of the reinforcement decreases the mechanical strength of the composites [10]. Figure 1 shows the variation of the maximum stress and tensile modulus to the rPP and formulated composites.

Fig. 1. Tensile properties of the experimental conditions: (a) Variation of the maximum stress and (b) tensile modulus to the rPP and formulated composites. Averages followed by the same letter do not differ, according to Tukey's test ($p \leq 0.05$).

For the compositions of 10% and 20% m/m of alkalized and bleached microfibers showed a change in the maximum stress (Figure 1a) of 11.6% (rPP-10Fa), 16.0% (rPP-20Fa), 8.1% (rPP-10Fb) and 13.0% (rPP-20Fb), which is higher than the same formulations of untreated microfiber composites. This may be associated with the increase in the wettability of the substrate and slight increase in the maximum stress of the composites is due to the probable breakdown of the lignocellulosic bundles, reduction of the content of lignin, hemicellulose, and moisture, due to the surface treatment of the fibres [11]. Figure 1b shows that the addition of microfibers in rPP matrix has a significant increase in tensile modulus of 51.6% and 43.2% for values of 10% and 20% m/m of microfibers, respectively, in the untreated compositions. The same quantities of alkalized microfibers have 115.4% and 138.7%; and bleached 158.7% and 137.4% higher modulus than the thermoplastic matrix.

It can be observed that when the concentration of microfibers in the composites increases, there is a slight reduction in flexural strength (Figure 2a), this can be attributed to a low dispersion and high stiffness of the secondary phase. The flexural modulus (Figure 2b) was remarkably higher for the composites compared to the rPP matrix. Noteworthy to mention that the stiffening load reduces the yield stress in the ductile rPP matrix, increasing the tensile and flexural modulus for all the composites. The results obtained by adding alkalised and bleached

microfibres were higher than the rPP matrix. 23-30% in maximum stress and 72-81% in flexural modulus for 10% m/m formulations, to alkalised and bleached respectively.

Fig. 2. Flexure properties of the experimental conditions: (a) Variation of maximum stress and (b) flexural modulus for rPP and formulated composites. Averages followed by the same letter do not differ, according to Tukey's test ($p \leq 0.05$).

When analysed the composites reinforced with microfibers, these showed a decrease in impact strength with the increase of the residue from 10% to 20% m/m (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Impact strength of rPP and formulated composites. Averages followed by the same letter do not differ, according to Tukey test ($p \leq 0.05$).

This may be associated with a possible agglomeration of microfibers, evidencing possible problems of reinforcement dispersion in the composite, which may negatively affect the load transfer and the propagation of cracks in the samples. The micrographs of the composites with alkalized (Figure 4b) and bleached (Figure 4c) microfibers have better mechanical adhesion between matrix-reinforcement.

Fig. 4. Fracture surface morphology of injected composites specimens: (a) rPP-20F, (b) rPP-20Fa e (c) rPP-20Fb.

The micrographs in Figure 4 support the results obtained in the tensile and flexural tests, for composites with 20% m/m microfiber portions, where there is a prevalence of fragile fracture surface. The yellow arrows indicate the disbonding of the dispersed phase from the thermoplastic matrix (Figure 4a) and, the probable matrix-reinforcement interfacial adhesion represented by the white circles, which are the result of the NaOH 10% m/v and NaClO 12% m/v treatments. No perceptible variations in the melting temperature (T_m) of the rPP (167.21°C) when eucalyptus microfibers were added. This agrees with the studies performed by Spadetti *et al.* [12] with eucalyptus cellulose fibres/rPP (168.14°C). Likewise, a decrease in the degree of crystallinity can be observed with the insertion of microfibers for both composites, with the lowest Xc% being 33.0% (rPP-10F) and 40.3% for rPP. The melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) of polypropylene in the composites showed a decrease for any series of the composites studied, from 84.3 J g⁻¹ (rPP) to 55.2 J g⁻¹ (rPP-20F), indicating an inhibitory effect on crystallisation.

4. Conclusions

The main conclusions of this study are: i. The composite materials made by recycled polypropylene matrix (rPP) reinforced with untreated eucalyptus microfibers (10% and 20% m/m) showed higher tensile modulus (51.6% and 43.2%) than the rPP matrix; ii. In contrast, the highest tensile modulus of composites reinforced with alkalinized (115.4% and 138.7%) and bleached (158.7% and 137.4%) microfibers were obtained for 10% and 20% m/m, respectively; iii. The composite materials reinforced with untreated eucalyptus microfibres showed an increase of 63.5% and 74.4% in flexural modulus with the increase of microfibres in the rPP matrix; iv. Alkalinized and bleached microfibers promoted increases of 23-30% in the maximum stress and 72-81% in the flexural modulus (10% m/m), respectively, when compared to the rPP matrix; v. Low concentrations of reinforcement promoted higher average Izod impact strength in the composites. Finally, the thermoplastic matrix crystallinity degree decreased with the increase of the reinforcement percentage, both for the composites containing treated and untreated fibres.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

CRediT author statement

R Maziero: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Formal Analysis; Writing – original draft. **JCC Rubio:** Conceptualisation; Methodology; Supervision; Writing – review. **LMG Vieira:** Supervision; Writing – review.

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